

BLUEMISSIONAA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

BLUEMISSIONAA CITIZEN CAMPAIGN- Report 01

The Inagural Citizen Campaign

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AIR Centre	Atlantic International Research Centre
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The inaugural BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign aimed to mobilise citizens, civil society, as well as organisations, associations, NGOs, school programs, companies, universities, research centres, and Mission projects involved in the preservation and restoration of the Atlantic and Arctic marine and coastal ecosystems and biodiversity. The campaign showcased groundbreaking solutions for restoration in distinct environments, spanning the Atlantic and Arctic, with positive impact on the well-being of European citizens. This initiative was developed within the framework of Work Package (WP) 5 - Citizen Engagement and Knowledge Transfer, under the Task 5.2 - Citizen Engagement and cross-fertilisation with Lighthouse CSA's. The event was conducted online via the video conferencing platform Zoom on October 6 2023, from 13:00 to 15:00 UTC, as part of the Atlantic International Research Centre (AIR Centre)'s weekly webinar series, [Networking Friday](#), attracting more than 130 registration from 49 countries and a total of 43 active participants attending the event. The session can be accessed on [YouTube](#), and it has garnered around 90 views four days after the event. Those numbers show the relevance and importance of offering citizen engagement opportunities related to the EU Mission in the Atlantic and Arctic basin. The detailed programme is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Citizen Campaign Agenda

1:00-1:05	Opening remarks and BlueMissionAA Overview , José Moutinho
1:05-1:15	Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse Presentation , Claudia Pecoraro
1:15-1:30	Keynote Speech – Best practices in stakeholders and citizen engagement , Nicole Biebow
1:30-2:30	Engaging citizens in ecological restoration solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none">o Restoration of macroalgae-dominated habitats at Madeira Island - Susanne Schäfero Coastal restoration with nature-based solution and people with the mobilisation in the Arctic Archipelago - Vera Hausnero Artificial reef 3D printing for Atlantic Area - Elena Blancoo Engaging citizens in Ecological Restoration Solutions in the Thames River - John Bryden
2:30 – 2:55	Q&A moderated by José Moutinho
2:55 - 3:00	Closing

This session was delivered by experts in citizen engagement from projects funded by both the European Union and non-European Union sources. The experts' biographies are shown in **Table 2**. The event aimed to achieve its primary objectives by bringing together experts, organisations, and citizens, with the following aims:

- Promote awareness and understanding of the role of Citizen Science in the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030," particularly in the Atlantic and Arctic basins.
- Showcase successful case studies and projects dedicated to restoring the ocean and waters in the coming decade.
- Facilitate networking opportunities among stakeholders to encourage potential partnerships and collaborations.
- Inspire active citizen participation in the upcoming Citizen Engagement Campaign

Table 2: Panellists' Biography

Name: José Moutinho

Position: Chief Business & Networking Officer, AIR Centre

Biography: José Moutinho is a biologist, with a bachelor's degree in Zoology, graduated from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro in 1981; Architect, graduated from Santa Ursula University in Rio de Janeiro, in 1988, with equivalence conferred by the Faculty of Architecture of the Technical University of Lisbon in 1989; Master of Science in Engineering and Technology Management from the Institute of Innovation, Technology and Development Policies of Instituto Superior Tecnico in 2005. Currently, he is the Chief Business and Network Developer for the AIR Centre.

Name: Claudia Pecorraro

Position: Policy and Communication Officer of Healthy Seas and Ocean unit DG Research and Innovation, European Commission

Biography: Claudia Pecorraro is working in the European institutions, initially the European Parliament, she is currently a Policy Officer at the European Commission. She has been involved in many policy issues: bioeconomy, healthy systems, marine and maritime affairs. Her key expertise and transferable fall into Government Relations strategy development and execution, stakeholder relations, advocacy/lobbying for preferred regulation, negotiation, internal and external communications, project management including budget and resources, team leadership, people development and coaching.

Name: Nicole Biebow

Position: Head of International Cooperation Unit,AWI

Biography: Nicole Biebow leads the International Cooperation Unit at the Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI) in Germany and is responsible for the international relations of the AWI. She maintains an extensive network of contacts in the European/International science and policy communities. Nicole the Coordinator of the EU project EU-PolarNet 2, having previously served as Executive Manager of EU-PolarNet 1. She has been also the Coordinator of the EU-funded Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium and will be the coordinator of the recently granted POLARIN (Polar Research Infrastructure Network) Horizon Europe project. In October 2021, she was elected as the chair of the European Polar Board an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic. Nicole received her PhD in Marine Geology at GEOMAR in Kiel.

Name: Susanne Schäfer

Position: Post-Doctoral Fellow and a member of MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre Madeira

Biography: Susanne completed her bachelor's and master's degrees at the Christian-Albrechts-University and the GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research in Kiel, Germany. Her master's thesis was part of GAME 2015, an international student exchange program of GEOMAR, which she carried out on Madeira Island, Portugal. In 2017, Susi started her PhD project, which focuses on non-indigenous species and their distributional shifts due to temperature changes and extreme events. She analyses temperature data to describe general trends and extreme events at Madeira Island and runs mesocosm experiments. From 2019 to 2021, Susi was a researcher in the GoJelly project; she took care of jellyfish cultures and conducted ecological trials on different life stages of jellyfish. Furthermore, she is a member of the scientific diving team of MARE and assists with monitoring and underwater visual censuses (UVC).

Name: Vera Hausner

Position: Head of Arctic Sustainability Laboratory, University of Tromsø

Biography: Vera Hausner earned her master degree in Environmental Science, University of Lancaster, England and her doctorate degree in natural resource management from Univ. Her research interest is in the environmental and natural resource management in circumpolar areas. Working with driving forces for ecosystem changes and management in both tundra and birch forest areas. Is project manager for a major interdisciplinary project on changes in circumpolar tundra areas in Norway, Russia, Canada and Alaska.

Name: Elena Blanco

Position: PhD Civil Engineer in the Construction Technology Applied Research Group (GITECO) at Universidad de Cantabria

Biography: Since 2005, Elena Blanco is the head of the 3D printing research line and has participated in different projects regarding sustainable mortars apt for 3D printing to be used as artificial reefs.

Name: John Bryden

Position: Head of Improving Rivers of Thames21

Biography: John is head of river improvements at Thames21. He came to Thames21 from the Environment Agency, where he worked for seven years leading river restoration, wetland, and SuDS projects. He may be appeased with offerings of cricket bats and tea.

In fostering active citizen engagement and contributing to the collective Mission of ocean and water restoration, this report serves as a comprehensive documentation of the inaugural citizen campaign. This document offers a detailed account of the campaign's objectives, key activities, outcomes, and recommendations that pave the way for future initiatives.

2. Key Activities

The inaugural BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign demonstrated some innovative solutions, success stories, Q&A sessions, and scaling up and replication opportunities for marine restoration from different environments across the Atlantic and the Arctic as follows:

- Moderation by José Moutinho from the BlueMissionAA project (**Figure 1**)
- EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” by Claudia Pecoraro (**Figure 2**)
- Best practices and Lessons Learned from stakeholder engagement in EU-PolarNet by Nicole Biebow (**Figure 3**)
- Restoration of macroalgae-dominated habitats at Madeira Island presented by Susanne Schäfer (**Figure 4**)
- Coastal restoration with nature based solution and people in the Arctic Archipelago by Vera Hausner (**Figure 5**)
- Artificial reef 3D printing for Atlantic Area by Elena Blanco (**Figure 6**)
- Engaging citizens in Ecological Restoration Solutions in the Thames River delivered by John Bryden (**Figure 7**)
- Q&A session with all speakers (**Figure 8**)

Figure 1: Opening session moderated by José Moutinho

Figure 2: EU Mission “Restore Our Ocean & Waters”

Figure 3: Best Practices and Lessons Learned from EU-PolarNet by Nicole Biebow

Figure 4: Restoration of macroalgae habitats at Madeira Island from CLIMAREST project by Susanne Schäfer

Figure 5: Coastal restoration with nature and people from A-A AGORA by Vera Hausner

Figure 6: Artificial reef 3D printing for Atlantic area 3DPARE by Elena Blanco

Figure 7: Engaging Citizens in Ecological Restoration Solutions from Thames21 by John Bryden

Figure 8: Q&A session of Citizen Campaign

3. Outcomes

This report on the outcomes of the BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign provides a comprehensive overview of the campaign's objectives and the resulting impacts. Delving into the outcomes, it reveals the increasing awareness of the EU Mission, success stories, lessons learned, and the groundwork laid for sustained engagement in the vital objective of preserving and restoring the Atlantic and Arctic Basins. The details are as follows:

- The event attracted 43 participants from different countries. Attendees varied from concerned citizens, organisations, associations, NGOs, school programs, companies, universities, research centres, sister projects, and other citizen science initiatives involved in the protection and restoration of the Atlantic and Arctic oceans.
- Citizen campaigns have uncovered success stories, exemplifying the tangible impact of collective efforts in preserving and restoring our oceans. From innovative restoration approaches in diverse ecosystems to the active engagement of citizens in ocean conservation, these success stories showcase the multifaceted achievements of the projects. For instance, **Nicole Biebow** (AWI) shared her stories of how EU-PolarNet successfully created and implemented a strategic framework to prioritise science, enhance the utilisation of polar infrastructure, and establish new partnerships for co-designing research projects with tangible societal benefits. This involved a higher level of coordination in polar research and operations, fostering closer cooperation with international stakeholders. With this success, the EU-PolarNet initiative has continued as EU-PolarNet 2 with broader partners and goals which are to establish a sustainable and inclusive platform to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policy-making processes.
- The citizen campaign was the successful facilitation of networking opportunities among stakeholders. This resulted in the creation of an environment conducive during the event to fostering potential partnerships and collaborations. Through virtual networking sessions, participants had the chance to connect, share insights, explore synergies, and search for potential opportunities in the collaboration. This networking success is a testament to the campaign's commitment to building a collaborative community dedicated to the preservation and restoration of the Atlantic and Arctic Basins. The strengthened network serves as a foundation for future joint efforts and collective initiatives in addressing the challenges faced by these crucial marine ecosystems.
- Through engaging presentations, discussions, and the sharing of impactful success stories, the campaign effectively sparked enthusiasm among citizens to actively contribute to the Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030". This outcome stands as a testament to the campaign's ability to mobilise more than 40 active participants, fostering a sense of

shared responsibility and commitment to making a positive impact on the health of our oceans and waters. During Q&A sessions, the enthusiasm of participants for the opportunity to scale up and replicate the presented projects of the Atlantic and Arctic Basins in their home countries became the main discussion topic.

4. Recommendations

The BlueMission AA Citizen Campaign has concluded with recommendations on how projects can effectively engage stakeholders and citizens for success. Engaging both groups is crucial for meaningful and lasting change in preserving the Atlantic and Arctic Basins. This report summarises success stories and highlights the importance of stakeholder and citizen involvement in advancing research and projects for the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”. The report categorises engagement into two contexts. Firstly, in stakeholder engagement, four main aspects are outlined for organising these activities.

1. **Consideration of societal relevance.** Incorporating societal relevance into stakeholder engagement involves acknowledging and addressing the impact of engagement activities on broader society. It is important to consider how the engagement process and its outcomes affect the well-being, needs, and concerns of the community or society as a whole.
2. **Evaluation of relevance and interest.** Evaluating relevance and interest in stakeholder engagement is crucial to ensure that the process effectively addresses stakeholders' concerns and maintains their engagement.
3. **Decision in the engagement format.** The specific format and steps for stakeholder engagement may vary depending on the nature of the project, the stakeholders involved, and the desired outcomes. The key is to ensure that the process is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to the needs and concerns of stakeholders.
4. **Commitment to engaging the stakeholders.** It refers to the dedication and determination to involve and collaborate with relevant individuals, groups, or organizations in a project, initiative or decision-making process. This commitment is important for building trust, fostering collaboration, and ensuring that stakeholders are actively and meaningfully involved in activities that affect them

Secondly, citizen engagement is an ongoing process, that should be adapted to the unique needs of each community or group who become the main subjects to engage. Building trust and active participation is key to its success. This report concluded 3 main aspects of engaging citizens. These main points are implicitly covered and suitable to be applied in stakeholder engagements and citizen engagement, whereas citizen engagement typically encompasses a broader public audience, including individuals who may not have a direct stake in the matter that the project and/or initiative are addressed to. Thus, these 3 main points are worth to consider in citizen engagement:

1. **Working with an intermediary to be the liaison to the project.** Working with intermediaries as liaisons can greatly enhance the reach and impact of your citizen engagement efforts by leveraging the trust and influence these intermediaries have within their communities
2. **Direct contact is preferred as the format of engagement.** Direct contact, whether face-to-face meetings, or one-on-one conversations, allows for a personal connection between citizens and project representatives. This personal touch can foster trust and a sense of being heard.
3. **Respect and recognition for cultural and historical origin.** This point signifies showing respect to a particular place or region to people and their sense of belonging to that area that becomes the subject of the project and/or the initiative, for example, acknowledging citizens' heritage and regions as their homeland. Acknowledging citizens' heritage and regions as their homeland is not only a sign of respect but also a way to empower citizens to actively engage in discussions and decisions that affect their communities. It contributes to a more inclusive and culturally sensitive citizen engagement process.

In general, there are 5 steps to follow for the success of stakeholder and citizen engagement:

1. **Know “who are our stakeholders”.** Stakeholders are individuals or entities who may be impacted by, concerned about, interested in, significant to, or have influence over the project's agenda. They can also be end-users of the project's outcomes.
2. **Identify the respected stakeholders and citizens** based on their specific needs, interests, importance and influence to the projects.
3. **Know the instrument to engage stakeholders.** Engaging stakeholders and citizens effectively often requires a combination of instruments or tools. These instruments should be selected based on the specific objectives of the engagement, the preferences and needs of the participants, and the context of the engagement.
4. **Commit to the agenda and learn from the lessons** that have been given by the stakeholders. By committing to the agenda and valuing the lessons offered by stakeholders, you can build trust, foster collaboration, and ensure that the engagement process remains responsive to the evolving needs and expectations of all parties involved.
5. **Open science and knowledge exchange.** The outcomes of stakeholder and citizen engagement will facilitate mutual learning about the process. This, in turn, will guide the trajectory of the research or initiative, enhance accountability, and, most importantly, contribute insights that inform policymaking and best practices in the field.

The recommendations gathered from our panelists' success stories in our inaugural citizen campaign validate the significance of our citizen campaign as a powerful tool for driving ocean restoration and conservation efforts. The lessons learned and insights shared will serve as a foundation for future engagement activities and strengthen the EU Mission "Restore our

Ocean and Waters by 2030" in the Atlantic and Arctic regions. The BlueMissionAA team are grateful to our panellists for their valuable contributions and look forward to continuing this journey of citizen empowerment and environmental stewardship. Therefore, the BlueMissionAA project is committed in consolidating and mobilising a wide community of relevant stakeholders and EU citizens towards the achievement of Mission objectives at basin level.

The inaugural citizen campaign went successfully and the BlueMissionAA team have gathered some opinions from the experts and teams during the event. Then, we have established some feedback for creating a better management of engaging citizens for the upcoming events. The feedback is delivered in details in the assessment of the citizen campaign.

5. Assessment of Citizen Campaign

Based on the insights and experiences gathered from the inaugural BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign, several recommendations are proposed for enhancing the effectiveness of forthcoming campaigns. These recommendations are divided into three categories: before, during, and after the citizen campaign. The details are described as follows:

a) Before citizen engagement

- Begin advertising the event at least three weeks prior to its scheduled date. This allows more time for potential participants to mark their calendars and plan their attendance. Additionally, enhance the utilisation of a multi-channel approach for promotion, including social media platforms and email newsletters. This wide-reaching strategy ensures that the event reaches a diverse audience and maximises attendance from various demographics.
- Use feedback/impact tools, such as surveys and questionnaires in the registration form, for citizens to share their opinions and ideas. This will aid in to better understand their expectations and the way to engage with BlueMissionAA.
- Consider direct contact as the format of engagement. This would allow the engagement activities to be done in a face-to-face meeting or for an opportunity to develop a hybrid engagement format. Personal interaction fosters the sense of credibility, community and empathy between the project partners and citizens and would therefore ensure the success of the project(s).
- Maintain consistent and regular citizen engagement, occurring every two months. This provides a reliable platform for citizens to consistently express their perspectives, address concerns, and offer suggestions. This creates an atmosphere where citizens feel more deeply involved and committed to the project.

b) During citizen engagement

- Find new strategies to deliver capacity-building activities to enhance participant engagement and create dynamic, participatory sessions to hear their opinions about the presented projects.

In addition to the new strategies, the delivery method can be varied, for example, a workshop. The suitability of a workshop approach depends on its purpose and the chosen methods for documenting and sharing the information derived from it. Various

effective workshop methods can be traditional town hall meetings, design thinking, scenario planning, participatory budgeting workshops, citizen panels or focus groups, storytelling workshops, and collaborative mapping.

- Encourage citizens to share personal stories. This activity is integral to knowledge transfer, as stories serve as a powerful tool for conveying information and establishing connections.
- Promote networking opportunities within and outside of communities. This facilitates knowledge sharing, the exchange of experiences, and input on effective community engagement strategies.

c) After citizen engagement

- Obtain feedback from participants and make necessary adjustments to enhance the overall experience. This iterative evaluation cycle is critical for continuous improvement and ensuring that the engagement process aligns with participants' needs and expectations.
- At the culmination of each session, participants could receive certificates acknowledging their active participation and valuable contributions.
- Utilise data and insights garnered from the process to tailor new approaches to regional and cultural specifics, avoiding one-size-fits-all models. The iterative nature of citizen engagement demands practitioners to adapt strategies and to optimise platforms, archives, and outreach methods based on feedback and evolving data.

6. Conclusions

The inaugural BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign demonstrated the potential of citizen engagement in the preservation and restoration of the Atlantic and Arctic marine ecosystems. Through a diverse range of presentations, discussions, and Q&A sessions, the event succeeded in raising awareness, showcasing success stories, and fostering collaborative networks.

With more than 130 registrations and 43 participants representing various stakeholders, including concerned citizens, organisations, NGOs, and academic institutions, the campaign provided a platform for meaningful interactions and knowledge exchange. The success of this event serves as a testament to the commitment and dedication of individuals and organisations towards the shared goal of restoring our oceans.

As we move forward, it is imperative to heed the recommendations outlined in this report to further enhance the effectiveness of future campaigns. By leveraging the insights gained from this inaugural event, we can continue to build a vibrant and engaged community dedicated to the restoration and preservation of the Atlantic and Arctic Basins.

In conclusion, the BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign serves as a model for collaborative, citizen-driven initiatives in marine conservation. Its success underscores the importance of continued citizen engagement and knowledge transfer in achieving the ambitious goals set forth by the EU Mission.

2023